

An Analysis of the Problems Faced by the Entrepreneurs of Small Enterprises in Availing Bank Finance

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Abstract:

The entrepreneurs of small enterprises are challenged with a number of problems right from the beginning of their enterprises and these are insufficient credit facility, infrastructural bottlenecks, technology obsolescence and competitive environment etc. Small business owners can obtain the operating cash they need from commercial banks, community banks, local rural banks, and government-run financial institutions. The banking organizations primarily provide operating capital that is required. Banks make important contribution in providing the entrepreneurial finance to small enterprises. Banks provide finance to entrepreneurs to establish a new unit, expand the business activities and diversify the business. In the present study, the problems of small enterprises in Availing bank finance are tested by yes or no question. A sample of 76 respondents has been selected.

This research paper helps to understand the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance. This paper is useful for the students, the teachers and the managers of educational institutions to understand the problems of entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance. It is also useful to policy makers like government for formulating favourable policy to understand the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises. Research scholars can also use this paper for further research. Thus, all the stakeholders will come to know more about the problems faced by the entrepreneurs in availing bank finance.

Keywords: Bank Finance, Entrepreneurs, Small Enterprises, Problems.

Introduction:

The entrepreneurs of small enterprises are challenged with a number of problems right from the beginning of their enterprises and these are insufficient credit facility, infrastructural bottlenecks, technology obsolescence and competitive environment etc. Small business owners can obtain the operating cash they need from commercial banks, community banks, local rural banks and government-run financial institutions. The banking organizations primarily provide operating capital that is required. Banks make important contribution in providing the entrepreneurial finance to small enterprises. Banks provide finance to entrepreneurs to establish a new unit, expand the business activities and diversify the

business. The entrepreneurs can make good the insufficiency of funds by using the funds provided by the banks. They can raise required working capital from commercial banks, cooperative banks, private banks and regional rural banks. The banking system provides mainly working capital. Other financial assistance is also available to the small enterprises. Small enterprises sector has been a dynamic and vibrant sector of Indian economy in general and industrial sector in particular. It is an important constituent of Indian economy and of total industrial sector in particular. The small enterprises sector acts as a cradle to appreciate not only the grass root of entrepreneurial talent but also to provide employment opportunities at the local

level. Small enterprises have solved the problems of poverty and unemployment to some extent.

They need low investments, offer a method of ensuring a more equitable distribution of national income and facilitate effective mobilization of capital and skill. They stimulate the growth of industrial entrepreneurship and promote a more diffused pattern of ownership and location. Small enterprises contribute significantly to employment generation, dispersal of industrial activity to rural and backward areas, facilitating the all-round economic growth by value addition, ensuring the mobilization of local capital and developing entrepreneurial skills.

Supply of finance is the most significant component for progress of any business activity. It makes a decisive contribution in accomplishment of activities for which bank plays an important role in development of various areas of economy. It mainly provides required financial help for different sectors to develop in economy. Thus, the core objective of bank is to easily disburse sufficient finance to small enterprises like other sectors also. But decentralized lending by commercial banks is not easy to evaluate as well as impact of that funding on economy is also difficult to evaluate.

Statement of the Problem:

The supply of credit is most important component for the development of any business activity. It plays a decisive role in accomplishment of activities for which banks play an important role in development of various areas of economy. Particularly, the development of small enterprises is hampered by the lack of money. The researcher has focused on the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance in the study area. Thus, the main objective of the banks is to easily provide adequate finance to small enterprises. But, scattered lending by commercial banks is difficult to evaluate. The impact of that funding on economy is also difficult to evaluate. The present study attempted to analyse the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in

availing bank finance in the study area. This factor is having impact on financial stability the small enterprises and it leads to economic development of the country.

Objectives:

1. To Analyse the Problems faced by the Entrepreneurs of Small Enterprises in Availing Bank Finance in the study area.

Hypotheses:

H₀: The Entrepreneurs of Small Enterprises are Not Facing any Problems in getting Bank Finance in the study area.

Methodology:

The research methodology of this research paper comprises of collecting the data from primary sources and secondary sources. The primary data are collected with specific reference to the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance in the study area. All the necessary secondary data were collected from library study such as books, magazines, journals, periodicals, newspapers and websites. In the present study, problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance is tested by yes of no question. A sample of 76 respondents has been selected.

The primary data were collected from seventy-six entrepreneurs of small enterprises in Sindhudurg district, who have registered their units with the District Industries Centre, Sindhudurg. Parameter used is the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance in the study area. Accordingly, interpretations and inferences were drafted.

Significance of the Study:

Entrepreneurs of small enterprises can obtain the needed operating funds from commercial banks, community banks, local rural banks and government-run financial institutions. The banking

organizations primarily provide operating capital small enterprises. Banks make important contribution in providing the entrepreneurial finance to small enterprises. Banks provide finance to entrepreneurs to establish a new unit, expand the business activities and diversify the business.

This research paper helps to understand the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance. This paper is useful for the students, the teachers and the managers of educational institutions to understand the problems of entrepreneurs of small enterprises in availing bank finance. It is also useful to policy makers like government for formulating favourable policy to understand the problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises. Research scholars can also use this paper for further research. Thus, all the stakeholders will come to know more about the problems faced by the entrepreneurs in availing bank finance.

Limitations of the Study:

The paper is limited only to the problems faced by the entrepreneurs in availing bank finance. The primary data were collected in November and December, 2025. This paper is based on the perceptions given by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in Sindhudurg district. Required secondary data is collected from books, journals, reports, newspapers and websites.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The small entrepreneurs have faced many problems in getting loans from the banks. It affects the financial health of the small enterprises. In the present study, the problems in getting loans from the banks are confined to the high interest rate of the bank loans, insufficient quantum of loans, cumbersome formalities, delay in disbursement, margin money problems, security related problems, indifferent attitude of the officials, insistence of collateral security. A sample of 76 respondents has been selected and data collected from them have been organized in the following table for analysis.

Table 1: The Problems Faced in Getting Loans from Banks

S. N.	Particulars	High Interest		Insufficient Loan		Formalities		Delay in Disbursement		Margin Money		Security		Indifferent Attitude		Collateral	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
a) On the Basis of Location																	
i	Devgad	5	71	4	57	6	86	5	71	3	43	3	43	4	57	2	29
ii	Vaibhavwadi	2	100	2	100	2	100	1	50	1	50	1	50	1	50	1	50
iii	Kankavali	14	78	7	39	14	78	7	39	5	28	9	50	6	33	5	28
iv	Malvan	2	100	1	50	2	100	1	50	1	50	1	50	0	0	0	0
v	Vengurla	0	0	1	50	1	50	1	50	0	0	1	50	2	100	1	50
vi	Kudal	13	39	9	27	19	58	16	48	13	39	16	48	9	27	9	27
vii	Sawantwadi	1	10	3	30	9	90	6	60	4	40	5	50	4	40	2	20
viii	Dodamarg	1	50	0	0	1	50	0	0	1	50	1	50	0	0	1	50
	Total	38	50	27	36	54	71	37	49	28	37	37	49	26	34	21	28
b) On the Basis of Type of Organisation																	
i	Proprietary	25	52	19	40	38	79	29	60	21	44	26	54	19	40	18	38
ii	Partnership	5	42	4	33	6	50	4	33	3	25	6	50	5	42	1	8
iii	Pvt Ltd Co.	8	50	4	25	10	63	4	25	4	25	5	31	2	13	2	13
	Total	38	50	27	36	54	71	37	49	28	37	37	49	26	34	21	28
c) On the Basis of Nature of Activity																	
i	Manufacturing	19	45	16	38	28	67	19	45	14	33	18	43	14	33	10	24
ii	Service	19	56	11	32	26	76	18	53	14	41	19	56	12	35	11	32
	Total	38	50	27	36	54	71	37	49	28	37	37	49	26	34	21	28

Source: Primary Data. Note: Multiple Responses.

Graph 1: The Problems Faced in Getting Loans from Banks

The table 1 and graph 1 show the problems faced by entrepreneur while getting loans from banks. It is observed that cumbersome formalities (71%), high interest rate (50%), delay in disbursement (49%) and the security related problems are the some of the common problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in the study area in getting loans from the banks. Most of the entrepreneurs of proprietary business (79%) have facing the problem

It is inferred that when it comes to the understanding the problems faced by the entrepreneurs in getting loans from banks, they were asked certain problems like the high interest rate of the bank loans, insufficient quantum of loans, cumbersome formalities, delay in disbursement, margin money problems, security related problems, indifferent attitude of the officials, insistence of collateral security etc which they are suffering from. After analysis, it can be inferred that out of various problems considered, ‘cumbersome formalities’ is the major problem faced by the entrepreneurs in getting the loans from the banks.

Hypothesis Testing:

In the present study, the researcher has framed the working hypothesis to analyse the major problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises in the study area.

of cumbersome formalities in getting loans from the banks. Most of the entrepreneurs of manufacturing units (67%) and service sector units (76%) have faced the problem of cumbersome formalities in getting loans from the banks. It is inferred that the entrepreneurs of small enterprises are facing certain problems while getting the loans from the banks like cumbersome formalities, high interest rate, insufficient loan, delay in disbursement etc.

The entrepreneurs of small enterprises do not face the problems in availing the bank finance in the study area.

To test this hypothesis, the researcher has incorporated this variable in the questionnaire. The problems in availing the entrepreneurial finance from banks by entrepreneurs of small enterprises are confined to high rate of interest for bank loans, insufficient quantum of loan, cumbersome formalities, delay in disbursement of loan, margin money problems, security related problems, indifferent attitude of the officials and insistence of collateral security. The response options were Yes and No type, where close ended questions were framed. The list of the statements is given in the respective tables. The researcher has framed following statistical hypotheses:

H_0 : The entrepreneurs of small enterprises do not face any significant problem in availing the bank finance in the study area.

H₁: The entrepreneurs of small enterprises face significant problems in availing the bank finance in the study area.

H₀: p = 50

H₁: p > 50

This null hypothesis is tested by using Z test in the following table:

Table 2: Analysis of Problems in getting Loan form Banks

Statement	p	q	n	Standard Error of p	Observed Sample Proportion of Problem Faced P [^]	Calculated Z value	Accept /Reject H ₀
a) High Rate of Interest for bank loans	38	38	76	0.057354	0.5	0	Accept
b) Insufficient Quantum of Loan	27	49	76	0.057354	0.355263	-2.5236	Accept
c) Cumbersome Formalities	54	22	76	0.057354	0.710526	3.67065	Reject
d) Delay in Disbursement	37	39	76	0.057354	0.486842	-0.2294	Accept
e) Margin Money Problems	28	48	76	0.057354	0.368421	-2.2942	Accept
f) Security Related Problems	37	39	76	0.057354	0.486842	-0.2294	Accept
g) Indifferent attitude of the officials	26	50	76	0.057354	0.342105	-2.753	Accept
h) Insistence of collateral security	21	55	76	0.057354	0.276316	-3.9001	Accept

Source: Primary data

Test Results:

The results of the analysis are very interesting. The test results indicate that the entrepreneurs of small enterprises do not face significant problems in terms of a) high rate of interest for bank loans (Z= 0 Accept null hypothesis), b) insufficient quantum of loan (Z= -2.5236 Accept null hypothesis), d) delay in disbursement (Z= -0.2294 Accept null hypothesis), e) margin money Problems (Z= -2.2942 Accept

However, it is noteworthy that the results indicate that the entrepreneurs of small enterprises faced the significant problem in terms of completing cumbersome formalities for availing loans. Here for the statement c) cumbersome formalities (Z= 3.67065 Reject null hypothesis) revealing that it is significant problem faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises. It is also confirmed with red-tapism problem faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises (Table 1). It is observed that the majority of the entrepreneurs of small enterprises (74%) have faced the problem of red-tapism. From

null hypothesis), f) security related problems (Z= -0.2294 Accept null hypothesis), g) indifferent attitude of the officials (Z= -2.753 Accept null hypothesis), h) insistence of collateral security (Z= -3.9001 Accept null hypothesis). For all these parameters the calculated Z value is lesser than 1.64 indicating no significant problems faced by the entrepreneurs of small enterprises for the specified parameter.

the above, it can be said that **the hypothesis, the entrepreneurs of small enterprises do not face the problems in availing the bank finance in the study area, stands accepted.**

On the basis of the results of hypothesis testing, it can be inferred that out of the different problems considered, only one problem i.e., cumbersome formalities is faced significantly. Therefore, it can be concluded that the entrepreneurs of small enterprises do not face the problems in availing the bank finance.

Findings And Suggestions:

It is observed that the entrepreneurs of small enterprises are facing certain problems while getting the loans from the banks like cumbersome formalities, high interest rate, insufficient loan, delay in disbursement etc. After analysis, it can be inferred that out of various problems considered, 'cumbersome formalities' is the major problem faced by the entrepreneurs in getting the loans from the banks.

It is suggested that the banks should minimize the unnecessary documentation and cumbersome formalities, so that they can finance quickly and adequately. This will help to overcome the problem of delay in sanctioning the loan to the entrepreneurs and the banks will be found more efficient. It is also suggested that, if possible, the banks should try minimize the other charges imposed for giving banking services to the entrepreneurs. This will not only help to reduce the cost of raising funds by way of loans from banks and the entrepreneurs will get economical loans.

Conclusion:

The small enterprises provide the employment to the society and bring prosperity in the nation through industrial and socio-economic development. The small enterprises can be developed by providing financial support on regular basis. Above mentioned suggestions or recommendations, if taken into account seriously

and implemented properly, it will not only help to improve the role of the banks in the study area, but also strengthen the relation between the banking institutions and the entrepreneurs of small enterprises.

References:

1. Ordon, E., & Natarajan, K. (2014). *Entrepreneurship Development*. Mumbai: Himalaya Publishing House.
2. Gupte, R. B. (2018). *Annual Report 2017-2018*. Ministry of Small Scale Industries, Msme-Development Institute. Mumbai: Government of India.
3. Kothari, C. R., & Garg, G. (2019). *Research Methodology Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
4. Malla, R. M. (2010). *SIDBI Report on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Sector, 2010*. Lucknow: Small Industries Development Bank of India.
5. Satpute, A. R. (2020). *Annual Credit Plan 2020-21 Sindhudurg District (MS)*. Zonal Office, Ratnagiri. Ratnagiri: Zonal Manager, Lead bank, Bank of India.
6. Shinge, R. R. (2020). *Economic Survey of Maharashtra-2019-20 Marathi*. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Planning Department. Mumbai: Government of Maharashtra.
7. Uike, D. D. (2012). *Entrepreneurship Development (Obstacles and Solutions)*. Mumbai: Himalaya Publishing House